

Recreational Facilities for Leisure and Pleasure in Shopping Mall in Pakistan

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Abstract

Shopping is a social activity that takes on many forms in various cultures. The goal of this study is to portray modern shopping as a modified form of recreation. It also tries to examine current buying behavior in light of the recreational facilities available to customers at a shopping mall and how they use them. To name a few, there is a food court, a play area, a fitness club, a Five-Dimensional (5D) movie theater, a baby chair, an atrium/exhibition hall, free Wi-Fi, and a cinema hall. These user-based amenities have arisen as distinguishing characteristics of shopping malls, emphasizing a mall's uniqueness. This study focuses on a few recreational facilities and then narrows down to recreational facilities sub-categories at a specific retail mall called Emerald Mall. The data is collected quantitatively and qualitatively and presented statistically, with the findings analyzed using criteria relevant to shopping mall quality as a whole. The findings include the identification of inadequate facilities in the food court, play area, and fitness club. At first, there was a Jest Five-Dimensional (5D) movie theatre, but now it is not available. Furthermore, a baby chair, an atrium/exhibition hall, free Wi-Fi, and a cinema hall were missing. The chosen mall needs improvement in a number of areas, while others have already been established. The research suggests making design changes in the chosen mall in order to solve the detected inconsistencies. It provides a framework and modular analysis of selected studies for a contextual approach to the development of the architectural design.

Index Terms: Attributes, Customers, Recreational Facilities, Shopkeepers, Shopping Mall.

I. INTRODUCTION

Basically, our whole lives revolve around work and recreation. However, in the interim, we must stop and trade our salaries for the things and services that allow us to enjoy both leisure and work. Shopping exhortation has been observed in user purchasing practice for many years [1]. Shopping incentives have been discovered to be determined by utilitarian and hedonic motivations. The functional and objective aspects of visiting a shopping mall are the subjects of utilitarian shopping motivation [2]. Hedonic motivation includes gratification, concepts, roles, experimentation, value, and social shopping. When visitors are in a bad mood, they go shopping for gratification to relax and release tension [3]. Since early man established permanent or semi-permanent dwelling structures and market areas, retail centers have pleasantly, effectively, and securely linked our lives together. Historically, shopping has always been a social activity. With the passage of time and user requirements, it was translated into a market but has now developed into shopping malls. These requirements may include several factors, with comfort being the most important of them. The comfort level can be increased and enhanced in design. Users of shopping malls in current times are more interested in shopping that provides need-based facilities, easy movement, and entertainment as compared to any rapid

and uneasy activity. This paradigm (pattern) shift has also inculcated the concept of attributes in shopping areas. Shopping malls, a modified form of open markets, thus have these characteristics that are likely to boost business on the one hand while increasing user comfort and satisfaction on the other.

Combining the two definitions, a shopping mall may be described as a structure that allows customers to stroll from one unit to another within the same building or set of buildings while conducting their business of trading products and services for money [4]. A management company constructs and maintains shopping malls as a single entity, which consists of a collection of independent retail establishments, services, and parking lots [5]. As a result, a shopping mall can be characterized as an enclosed place including a number of retail stores, restaurants, entertainment, and other companies with the shared goal of generating revenue. Private, off-street parking is available in shopping centers. On the other hand, shopping malls and hypermarkets have become essential components of the urban landscape. A bigger shopping mall can accommodate a wider range of stores and provide a more pleasant environment for consumers, encouraging them to return more frequently and stay longer. As a result of rising urbanization, there is a growing social need for environmentally friendly retail malls. Shopping malls began in urban locations, but they are now also found in

the suburbs of large cities, to meet the shopping demands of suburban communities distant from the core business district [6]. Large recreational shopping malls have been reported to stimulate frequent shopping by regular shoppers and tourists. The major qualities of shopping mall attractiveness are ease, leisure, variety, mall essence (heart), parking, and splendor [7]. The physical environment, comfort, and entertainment have completely mediated the relationship between ambiance and consumption, and they benefit both the environment and the customers. The built environment and entertainment are viewed as being critical to physical and social sustainability [8]. Shopping malls can help to promote social sustainability and can be used as quasi-public spaces. Attractions such as movie theatres, food courts, games, catwalks, and fashion shows can attract more visitors. These physical facilities, social activities, and safety in malls also have a positive impact on customers. Most of the customers come for entertainment and relaxation purposes [9]. The general perception of most shoppers is that besides shopping, entertainment, leisure, and time spent with friends and family are also purposes of visiting shopping malls.

Karachi is Pakistan's largest and most populated city, as well as the capital of Sindh province and the seventh largest metropolitan city on the planet. It is the main financial and industrial hub of Pakistan and also serves as a transport hub. Due to its location on the Arabian Sea, Karachi is also nicknamed the "City of Lights" and "The Bride of the Cities." The city's population is expected to reach 16,093,786 million people in 2020, making it the world's seventh biggest urban agglomeration and the largest metropolis in the Muslim world [10]. The city has several shopping malls, which help the customers. The appeal of a shopping mall can be based on a number of basic features that ultimately define the comfort level of a shopping mall for its users. The current study examined the attributes of a shopping mall in terms of recreational facilities. Amongst all the specific attributes of a shopping mall, the ones that act as the main frontline support for comfort level are the recreational facilities. If customers are unable to avail themselves of the facilities, the scope of their existence is questionable in terms of their functionality. The Emerald Mall is located in Block-5, Clifton, Karachi, which is one of the urbanized zones with a dense population and aims to provide a shopping facility for the local people. As an important shopping mall in the city, some of its user facilities need to be analyzed to ensure their best usage has a positive effect on shoppers. The study aims to survey selected attributes of Emerald Mall, i.e., recreational facilities that are not widely available:

- The food court had enough seating space in a congested and small area for the customers.
- There was insufficient space and no informal seating in the play area at Emerald Mall.
- The fitness club was not situated in a suitable place; it was on the fourth floor; hence many respondents didn't know about the existence of the fitness club.

- At first, there was a Jest Five-Dimensional (5D) movie theatre, but now it is not available.
- Baby chairs, atriums, exhibition halls, and open space in the central area of a mall, Wi-Fi, and a cinema hall were not there.

It intends to assess these attributes to improve and facilitate better customer service for the customers.

The following are the research questions of the study:

1. What are the design considerations regarding recreational facilities?
2. Which sub-attributes of the selected user facility in the case study are synchronized with the standards?
3. How is the comfort level in this case study affected due to the availability of selected attributes?

The study focuses on the following main objectives:

1. To develop a theoretical framework that is contextually appropriate and flexible for the development of the architectural design of the shopping malls.
2. To study selected attributes of a shopping mall in terms of user facilitation, including recreational facilities.
3. To analyze the selected attributes of a selected case study with respect to the standards to access their compatibility with local socio-cultural needs.
4. To find out the effective impact of specific attributes on the user's comfort.

A. Rationale

The Shopping Mall facility considers several attributes at the basic and general levels. Some of the attributes are defining and are unavoidable, while some are allied in nature and enhance the basic facilities. Recreational facilities are the front attributes of shopping malls to attract customers and provide a better comfort level. With the passage of time, the facilities of Emerald Mall need to be evaluated for improvement in order to facilitate and assess end-user satisfaction to make it sustainable in the future. A structured assessment, in fact, provided the baseline to define the best possible performance of the selected attributes of the shopping mall translated into facilities. This assessment also provided a better insight into the existing situation while highlighting the possible problems and their suggested solutions.

B. Problem Statement

The existing spatial design of Emerald Mall in Karachi was organized with a limited number of attributes for customers. With an increase in population and a high influx of customers, its best performance in delivery and quality of service has suffered. Thus, there was a need to analyze its spatial design and highlight the issues in the light of recent trends and best practices/standards in order to improve it to sustain future usage considering the socio-cultural scenarios of the city. The study focused on attributes that are widely integrated into shopping malls

around the world. These included objectively selected attributes; recreational facilities, considering these as sub-attributes, for example, food court, play area, and fitness club. The Jest Five-Dimensional (5D) movie theatre was closed while research was conducted. Moreover, a baby chair, an atrium/exhibition hall, free Wi-Fi, and a cinema hall were missing. This analysis may lead to configuring the effective impacts of specific attributes.

These categories were selected on the basis of their availability in terms of facilitation on design and end-user preference for their presence in the malls to ensure ample time presence to have a complete feeling of shopping and leisure.

C. Significance of the Study

The study signifies the presence of attributes in shopping malls and highlights the paradigm (pattern) shift in the concept of shopping from a pure need-based activity to a social activity with respect to the local community and frequent end-users visiting the malls.

This ultimately helps the enhancement and introduction of new design concepts that are much more user-friendly and lead toward human-centered designs in commercialized activity centers, i.e., shopping malls.

D. Limitations

The research is limited to the ground floor and three floors of the building that are used for shopping activities. The study focused only on selected attributes of Emerald Mall: recreational facilities. The floors above, i.e., "Emerald Tower," are out of the scope of this research because of the changed activity in the area. It also de-limits the management staff of shopping malls as their movement and usage of the mall are very limited by the sample target.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The economic, geographical, and political conditions of any country have a direct effect on its population. In fact, economics is concerned with human needs such as comfort, convenience, and luxuries [11]. Humanity's national, foreign, and international relations are a part of political life [12]. If all the matters and conditions mentioned above are according to people's needs from which they can satisfy their energy for a well-organized social life, then it can be an indicator for the erection of a successful society. Shopping has always been there since people (men and women) learned to exchange goods and services for what they didn't have. Shopping is looking at, pricing, and purchasing products that are for sale. It's a transaction that involves both a buyer and a seller. Shopping was first done in open-air public venues, alongside other public events and activities. Shopping was combined with other daily activities such as cultural events, entertainment, and so on. Shopping is often a social activity that serves both practical and recreational reasons [13].

A shopping mall is a structure featuring retail units and linking pathways that allow people to easily go from one unit to the next. Shopping malls are defined as follows, based on a variety of definitions: Shopping malls are complexes that include stores with many departments and merchant units, as well as cafeterias, restaurants, amusement centers, cinema halls, exposition halls, banks,

pharmacies, and other similar businesses of all sizes, which are usually settled in the countryside and controlled from a single center [14]. A shopping mall is a place where consumers are in search of a location where they can relax. Expectations are a critical and decisive factor determinant of consumer behaviors, according to a marketing publication [15-22].

When people are happy with the mall's features, they spend more time there. The more delighted shoppers are with mall features, the longer they are likely to spend there. According to the research, the choice of which shopping mall to visit is based on the shopping mall's characteristics [23]. Shopping malls are viewed as modern, active, and lively centers of life that cater to a wide range of customer needs. In today's competitive retail economy, it's more important than ever to efficiently manage shopping malls and understand what draws people to them [24]. The limitation of this research is based on selected attributes of Emerald Mall; recreational facilities on the ground plus three floors of the building that are used for shopping activity.

The behavior of visitors in shopping malls in general and specifically for this research recommends that ease as a shopping mall's feature has a great effect when a mall is chosen for a visit [25]. Another study identified various shopping mall retail mix factors that influence shopping well-being, including functionality, convenience, comfort, shopping mall safety, leisure activities, shopping mall atmosphere, hygiene, and self-identification [26]. Therefore, it is critically reviewed that shopping mall attributes that act as the main front support are important, like utilitarian and hedonic values, which, in turn, provide customer satisfaction. The global standards to measure the efficiency and attributes of shopping malls are mentioned in the standards in Time-Saver Standards for Building Types. McGraw-Hill [27], Building for Everyone: A Universal Design Approach: Booklet 6 - Facilities in buildings [28], Building for Everyone: A Universal Design Approach: Booklet 7 - Building types [29], Building for Everyone: A Universal Design Approach: Booklet 8 - Building management [30] and Karachi Building and Town Planning Regulations-2002 Amended Up to Date March 2017 [31]. And also referred to by scholars as mentioned in Shopping malls attractiveness: a segmentation approach [32], Determining shopping mall visitors' perceptions on mall attributes [33], Attractiveness factors Influencing Shoppers; satisfaction, loyalty, and word of Mouth: An Empirical Investigation of Saudi Arabia shopping malls [34], The relationship between shopping mall attributes, customer satisfaction, and positive word-of-mouth: China visitors in Hong Kong [35] and Factors defining shopping experience: an analytical study of Dubai [36].

The critical review of the literature shows that there are a lot of requirements that need to be fulfilled for the benefit of the users, including utilitarian and hedonic values. Consumers are motivated by utilitarian variables such as efficiency and cost, according to a study in the field of shopping [37], but also by the need to fulfill hedonic requirements like pleasure, social engagement, and amusement [38]. Emotions experienced as a result of completing a task in the mall give birth to utilitarian shopping value. Hedonic consumption refers to the delight

and pleasure that a customer expects from a shopping mall visit, and it is consequently linked to feelings, ideas, and perceptions [39]. A more recent study looked at the effects of shopping on positive mall attitudes and word-of-mouth and discovered that hedonic value had a bigger influence on favorable mall attitudes and word-of-mouth than utilitarian shopping value [40]. According to the literature on the subject, there are three types of shopping stimulants: The three sorts of motivations are functional motivations, social motivations, and experience or hedonic motivations. Shopping is now regarded as a form of renewal that gives happiness and calm [41]. The shopping mall is frequently a recreational and social meeting place that appeals to both young and old people [42-44]. Shopping centers are believed to be "meeting places." [45]. Shopping malls have evolved into an important component of social and economic life, particularly in metropolitan cities around the world [46]. This change denotes a transition from traditional retailing and marketing to new-generation retailing and marketing that emphasizes product engineering and utility [47]. Customers at shopping malls, for example, visit for entertainment activities for enjoyment and leisure, which is consistent with the objective of the shopping experience [48]. The entertainment demands of today's metropolitan population are addressed, as are their purchasing needs, in shopping malls. These organized companies for shopping malls have combined leisure amenities such as dining areas, courts, play spaces, exhibitions, music, cinema halls, talks, calming aromas, and so on to enhance consumer experiences. Recreational facilities, such as eateries, movie theatres, and sports for electronic gaming, have a positive influence on bringing many people to shopping malls. According to a previous study, mall leisure is comprised of two elements: eating and drinking establishments, as well as entertainment programs and facilities [49]. Restaurants within shopping malls have also emerged as sub-units for consumer mass support in order for them to stay longer and in comfort [50]. To maintain the visitors' comfort, it is recommended that shopping mall layouts be straightforward and easy to grasp. This may be accomplished by using a focal point, such as the main court, as a focus for the visitor's attention. This may also be utilized for a variety of promotional activities and events, such as exhibits, fashion shows, and so on. Based on U.S. experiences, the most successful shopping mall designs have been the simplest, mainly T and L-shaped layouts [51]. A shopping mall's entertainment mix may include specialty event entertainment (such as movie theatres) and food courts (for example, restaurants). Visitors to shopping malls are encouraged to spend more time there because of these entertainment options [52]. According to another study, the management and repair of community amenities is the most important aspect in ensuring overall customer satisfaction; however, effective communication and successful promotional events are also important in maintaining customer satisfaction [53]. Therefore, it is concluded that a shopping mall's motivation in terms of user satisfaction or user comfort level can be translated into shopping mall attributes. For the scope of this research, these attributes are translated as "recreational facilities" for the scope of this research. These attributes present several considerations in the design of shopping

malls, which, in turn, provide customer satisfaction. In addition to this, it is also an important factor that visitors, while selecting any mall for shopping purposes, consider the provision of recreational facilities in the mall. Therefore, it is also concluded that shopping mall attributes, which act as the main support for comfort level, may also affect the working of a shopping mall. This critical analysis highlights the need for the development of a framework while considering the contextual approach. The literature review also highlights that there is a knowledge gap existing as there is no framework established to be used while designing shopping malls. Henceforth, the following theoretical framework is established through this research.

III. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The literature review has signified some of the attributes of shopping malls specifically relevant to the need-based facilities. It is also revealed from the literature review that the attributes of shopping malls should consider the contextual approach while developing the architectural design for this activity. Therefore, the theoretical framework developed here reflects the contextual approach which may further be used as a baseline for analysis of need-based facilities according to the specific context of the shopping mall considering, for instance, its location, outreach area, the civic approach of customers, etc., to name a few. This is important to establish here that architectural design constraints of context are different for individual sites as well, therefore this theoretical framework is beyond generalization, yet provides an appropriately wider room for the development of such types of facilities that are related to the needs of the customers. These attributes are summed up in the theoretical framework as shown in Table I.

Table 1: Theoretical Framework of Attributes

Most Frequent User	Selected Attributes	Sub- Attributes
Customers, Shopkeepers	Recreational Facilities	Food court
		Play Area
		Fitness club
		Baby chair
		Atrium/ Exhibition Hall
		Free Wi-Fi
		Cinema Hall

These attributes are selected for the conduct of further research.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The research mainly adopts a quantitative methodology for collecting data through a selected case study; however, it also caters to some qualitative data for value additions in the form of observations, site visits, photographs, and architectural drawings. The case study was selected in the city of Karachi. The secondary sources included literature reviews, which consisted of documents, i.e., publications, earlier research, reports, census, archives, books, personal records, and referential material available in relevance to the area of study. The primary sources included questionnaires separately structured for customers and

shopkeepers and observations (through site visits, photographs, and architectural drawings for reference). Following this, a checklist was developed in accordance with selected attributes, which is the combination of the standards as prescribed by different relevant sources available in the literature and observations. Both data collection sources were processed through the developed checklist of selected attributes. The responses from the questionnaires were collected and statistically processed for the findings. These findings were further analyzed to draw conclusions.

A. Justification for Selection of Case Study

Emerald Mall is located near Do Talwar in Clifton Block-5, Karachi. By responding to the expanding demands of both local corporate firms and multinationals, the Clifton area is swiftly converting into a facilitator for economic growth, development, and diversification. The mall is connected to the city's important/major areas. Public transportation is provided 24 hours a day, seven days a week. Emerald Mall is located in a safe and secure neighborhood frequented by the city's wealthy and renowned.

In this shopping mall, there is good parking inside and outside the building. The area of the shopping mall is not too big, so users are not suffering from long walks. Whereas the Emerald Mall's lack of vibrancy suggests that present user amenities are insufficient in every way to deliver a comfortable and pleasant atmosphere, this is why the number of customers in this retail mall is often fewer than in other shopping malls. If given as proposed by users and specified in standards, these facilities may be able to meet a wide range of customer needs.

B. Population

The population of the study is mainly users of the shopping mall. These users are subdivided into two categories: customers and shopkeepers. The management staff of the shopping mall is not included in the research as their movement and usage of the mall are very limited.

C. Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample consisted of two categories of users relevant to the type of population: customers and shopkeepers, regardless of the type of shop. The sample consists mainly of 210 participants in total. This includes 20 % of the total number of customers, which is equal to 180 out of 900 customers per day (as per record from the administration of Emerald Mall). The selection of customers was based on the level of interest of the customers in responding to the questionnaire questions. Large samples are usually used in descriptive research; the sample size is suggested to be 10 % to 20 % of the approachable population. While 30 shopkeepers were chosen from a sample of 90, it is recommended that at least 30 respondents be included in a sample because the number allows for the use of large sample statistics, which reduces the chance of standard error. The intention was to find out their experiences when using the shopping mall.

D. Formulating The Problem

Research focuses on formulating the problem based on the main attributes of shopping malls and recreational

facilities. It takes into account the further sub-sections of these selected attributes and thus attempts to find out the active functions of these sub-sections. The research questions are based on the basic formulated problem, which poses the question as to how the selected shopping mall benefitted or is deficient in terms of selected attributes.

E. Research Design

The primary goal of the research is to identify the issues related to comfort level and user satisfaction.

Figure I: Phases of Research

Figure II: Flow Diagram of Research Design

The data collection of Emerald Mall, Clifton, Karachi was carried out on site from February 2019 to September 2019 during multiple mall visits. The research design adopts the process of defining the objectives, which are translated into the research questions and observations. These research questions have defined the framework for the literature review, culminating in the feasibility of the research. It then follows the process of selecting a sample from the user population, conducted through a quantitative approach or method, as shown in figure I and figure II, above.

F. Research Instruments

The research uses two main instruments for the data collection process; firstly, questionnaires (for users, separately structured into two categories); and secondly, observations (for analysis of existing attributes through site visits, photographs, and architectural drawings for assessment).

G. Data Collection

Two types of data are gathered as part of this research: primary and secondary. The primary data sources are the questionnaires and observations (site visits, photographs, and architectural drawings) made on-site during the case study. The secondary data caters to the literature resources of multiple types, like books, articles, websites, newspapers, and more. A detailed survey on-site data collection consisted of producing baseline drawings of the building. This included the preparation of drawings to enable an environmental analysis of key aspects; measured drawings; and explanatory and analytical drawings. Attributes that achieve the goals and purposes of the shopping mall A local case study was selected for the research entitled Emerald Mall, Clifton, Karachi.

a) Site:

Emerald Mall is in Karachi's Clifton Block-5, on the 200-foot wide Khayaban-e-Iqbal double road, near Do Talwar, as shown in figure III. The region of Khayaban-e-Iqbal Clifton is quickly transforming into a facilitator for economic growth, development, and diversification by meeting the expanding demands of both local and foreign enterprises. The entire neighborhood is also scattered with numerous shopping malls, most of which are frequently crowded with shoppers throughout the year. All major schools and hospitals are near the site. All modes of public transportation are available 24 hours a day, seven days a week. With its planned high-rise business, residential, and shopping malls, it is one of the safest and most commercial areas in the city [54]. It is known as a residence for the city's wealthy and prominent residents. Clifton Beach, Pakistan's most popular beach, is located south of Clifton. Clifton can easily be reached via rail, road, and sea. The Karachi Cantonment Railway Station is located in the vicinity. While the neighborhood is connected with the rest of the city via a network of bridges, a boat can easily be hired to travel to Port Grand from Keamari Harbor or the DHA peninsula. The international airport is approximately 25 to 35 minutes away [55]. This Mall has a link to all the commercial roads in all locations, namely, Clifton, Defence, Saddar, and the main parts of Karachi, as shown in figure III. It is easily accessible from the Central

Business District CBD, I. I. Chundrigar Road, and premium residential areas like Civil Lines, Frere Town, Bath Island, Defence, Clifton, PECHS, Gulshan-e-Iqbal, Federal "B" Area, North Nazimabad, and others.

Figure III: Site of Emerald Mall, Clifton, Karachi showing the Growth Linkage with Surroundings [56]

b) Overview of the Emerald Mall:

Emerald Mall is being constructed at Do Talwar, Clifton, Karachi with a unique and innovative concept. The location of the mall is near the business hub of the city.

Figure IV: Emerald Mall is on Ground Plus Three Floors and Emerald Tower Offices are above Mall [57]

The overview of the chosen facility is given below:

- Name of the Shopping Mall: Emerald Mall.
- Design of Shopping Mall: Shamim Alam (SA Architects).
- Location: Khayaban-e-Iqbal, Clifton, Karachi.
- Year of Completion of Shopping Mall: 2010, December.
- Area of the Plot: $140' - 0'' \times 230' - 0'' = 32,200$ square feet (sq. ft.), $32,200/9 = 3,577$ square yards (sq. yd.), $3,577/4840 = 0.7392$ Acre.
- Building Type: Retail and Corporate Offices
- Height: Roof Height $180' - 0''$ and Antenna $236' - 0''$.
- Floors above Ground: 16 as shown in Fig. 4.
- Floor Underground: 1.
- Office Floors: 10.
- Shopping Floors: Ground, First, Second, Third, and Fitness Club/Gymnasium located on Fourth Floor.
- Parking Floors: 1 Basement and 4 Uppers.
- Timing: 11:00 am to 11:00 pm.

Selected Mall is a major commercial tower with a variety of facilities, including six passenger and cargo lifts, an electronic and staffed security system; and a firefighting system on each floor. An attractive architectural fair-face facade and an elegant exterior create a new business landmark [54]. Services, firefighting, security, and surveillance systems are as follows: The location is ideal. It is air-conditioned, has 100 % KESC electricity, and has 100 % self-generated backup power. Fire alarms, firefighting equipment, fire sprinklers, smoke detectors, and water hose reels are installed throughout the building on each floor, as well as in the plant room, control room, and sensitive areas. There are digital vehicle scanners, electronic and physical barriers, security checks, scanners, metal detectors, and hand-operated automated gates available at the main entrance. CCTV, security, and surveillance with staffed guards and a central security control monitoring room [58].

Figure V: View of Emerald Mall showing Customized Showrooms [59]

The ground floor, first floor, and second floor of Emerald Mall are entirely kept for customized showrooms as shown in figure V. The third floor, which is centrally air-conditioned and has six big kitchens with contemporary outlet countertops, is a symbol of progressive standards. A large food court is an extra benefit for Emerald Mall employees and visitors. On the third floor, there is also a children's play area and a prayer room. It was the first time in Pakistan that a Five-Dimensional (5D) movie theatre by Jest in Karachi was launched in this mall, but now it is not there [54]. The shopping mall has less consideration for pleasure, which gives a valid reason to frequent this mall.

c) Characteristics of Emerald Mall According to Selected Attributes:

The Mall is located in Clifton, Karachi, which is one of the urban zones with a dense population. This research aims to explain the importance of selected attributes in the performance of the spaces in the shopping mall. Emerald Mall was analyzed based on these selected attributes: It aims to consider these attributes so as to improve customer comfort and facilitate service for customers. On the third floor of Emerald Mall, the renovation was in progress in the food court. It was congested and small in size, as shown in figure VI. There was insufficient space and no informal seating in the play area as shown in figure VII. The fitness club was located in an inappropriate place. It was on the fourth floor, as shown in figure VIII. At first, there was a Jest Five-Dimensional (5D) movie theatre, but now it is not available. Also, a baby chair, an atrium/exhibition hall/open space in the central area of a mall, Wi-Fi, and a cinema hall were missing.

Figure VI: Renovation in Progress, Congested and Small Size Food Court on Third Floor of Emerald Mall

Figure VII: Insufficient Area and no Informal Seating in Play Area at Emerald Mall

Figure VIII: Fitness Club situated at Inappropriate Place, on the Fourth Floor of Emerald Mall

Thus, people did not seem to choose this shopping mall for the fact that there was some form of the minute recreational facility going on. This shows that recreational facilities are part and parcel of a shopping mall.

H. Interpretation of Data

The research focused on the analysis through a quantitative and qualitative approach collected through selected instruments (Questionnaires and Observations), i.e., through site visits, photographs, and architectural drawings. This approach is further analyzed and interpreted through a statistical method. Obtained data from the survey were analyzed. A comfort level of attributes was established. Analysis was important to get to conclusions.

V. ANALYSIS/FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

A. Analysis

a) Frequency of Usage of Food Court:

Figure X: Response of Shopkeepers about the Frequency of Usage of Food Court

The above figure IX and figure X graphical representations show that 4 % of respondents were satisfied with the indoor environmental conditions of the food court and used it every day, while 19 % of respondents used the food court twice a week, and 31 % of respondents used the food court once a week.

This is because they might be bringing food from home and do not want to go over budget. While 46 % of respondents said they used it rarely, a possible reason could be that they are not able to afford it and, hence, do not want to go over budget. Moreover, some shopkeepers may have health issues, so they may avoid the food from the court.

This space was under renovation while research was conducted during the period from February 2019 to September 2019 during multiple visits to the mall.

This is mentioned in Section-II: literature review; stated in standard [26] and referred to by scholars [31-35], [48], [49] and [51].

b) Food Court in Mall:

Figure XI: (a) Layout showing Location of Food Court on Third Floor of Emerald Mall (b and c) Food Court under Renovation on Third Floor

Figure XI: (a) Layout showing the Location of Food Court (b and c) Easily Accessible and Located on Correct Floor that is Third Floor of Emerald Mall

This query was not inquired from the customers; however, in relevance to this query, the next query was structured for both stakeholder groups.

Figure XII: Response of Customers to the Food Court in the Mall

The above figure XI and figure XII graphical representations show that 90 % of the respondents were satisfied with enough food in the food court, while 10 % responded that there was not enough food. 95 % of the users were also satisfied with how easily accessible it was, and 95 % of the respondents indicated that it was located on the right floor.

The food court was found to be crowded and small in size.

Figure XIII: Response of Shopkeepers to the Food Court in the Mall

The above figure XIII graphical representation shows that 95 % of the respondents were satisfied with enough food in the food court, while 5 % responded that there was not enough food. 100 % of the users were also satisfied with how easily accessible it was, and 85 % of the respondents indicated that it was located on the right floor.

While it was under renovation, research was conducted during the period from February 2019 to September 2019 during multiple visits to the mall.

This is also mentioned in Section-II: literature review; stated in standard [26] and referred to by scholars [31-35], [48], [49] and [51].

c) Activities in Play Area:

The below figure XIV and figure XV graphical representations show that 62 % of the respondents preferred electronic games, 28 % of the users were in favor of physical games, 5 % of the respondents preferred board games, and 5 % responded to any other, as shown in the figure.

Figure XIV: (a) Layout of a Play Area for Kids (b, c, d, and e) Play Area's door wide enough, without a Waiting Area, Small in Size, and Accessible to All

Figure XV: Response of Customers about the Activities in the Play Area

It was observed that there was insufficient space and no informal seating in the play area at Emerald Mall. The play area is near the food court, which is comfortable.

Figure XVI: Response of Shopkeepers about the Activities in the Play Area

The above figure XVI graphical representation shows that 60 % of the respondents preferred electronic games, 30 % of the users were in favor of physical games, and 10 % of the respondents preferred board games, while no one responded to any other, as shown in figure XVI. Since the shopkeepers come here daily for their jobs, they don't bring their kids with them.

This is mentioned in Section II: literature review; stated in standards [26], and referred to by scholars [33-35].

d) Use of Fitness Club:

Figure XVII: (a) Layout of Fitness Club on Fourth Floor (b, c, d, and e) Fitness Club not situated at a suitable place, on Fourth Floor of Emerald Mall

Figure XVIII: Response of Customers about the use of Fitness Club

The above figure XVII and figure XVIII graphical representations show that 0 % of respondents were using fitness clubs every day. 1 % of respondents were using them thrice a week, while 2 % of respondents were using them twice a week; these people are those who are well aware of the presence of a fitness club in the mall. 0 % of respondents were using it once a week, 0 % of respondents

were using it once a month, and 97 % of respondents never used it.

It was on the fourth floor, so many respondents didn't know about the existence of the fitness club.

Figure XIX: Response of Shopkeepers about the use of Fitness Club

The above figure XIX graphical representations show that 0 % of respondents were using fitness clubs every day and 0 % of respondents were using them three times a week. 5 % of respondents were using it twice a week, while 5 % of respondents were using it once a week. People use fitness clubs according to their needs. It was used by 0 % of respondents once a month, while 90 % never used it. Shopkeepers use the facility occasionally, but not very often.

This is also mentioned in Section II: literature review; stated in the standard [26].

e) Recommended Facilities in this Mall:

Figure XX: Response of Customers about the recommended Facilities in this Mall

The above figure XX graphical representation shows that 60 % of respondents suggested that there should be baby chairs, 80 % of respondents suggested that there should be an atrium/exhibition hall, 95 % of respondents suggested that there should be free Wi-Fi, and 70 % of respondents suggested that there should be a cinema hall. While 1 % of respondents suggested that there should be any other.

It was observed that at first there was a Jest Five-Dimensional (5D) movie theatre, whereas now it is not available. It was observed that baby chairs were not present in the mall.

This is mentioned in Section II: literature review; stated in standards [26] and [27].

The same is the case with the atrium/exhibition space, which was also not there. This is also mentioned in Section-II: literature review; stated in standard [28], and referred to by scholars [31-35], [48], [50-52].

In addition to this, free Wi-Fi was also not present. This is mentioned in Section II: literature review; stated in the standard [29].

Some of the other facilities that are not present in the mall are stated as the cinema hall. This is also mentioned in Section II: literature review; stated in the standard [30], and referred to by scholars [31-35] and [51].

Figure XXI: Response of Shopkeepers about the recommended Facilities in this Mall

The above figure XXI graphical representation shows that 10 % of respondents suggested that there should be a baby chair, 60 % of respondents suggested that there should be an atrium/exhibition hall, 100 % of respondents suggested that there should be free Wi-Fi, and 30 % of respondents suggested that there should be a cinema hall. While none of the respondents suggested that there should be any other.

While the observations about the questions inquired about are the same, the shopkeepers are much less concerned about the facilities discussed because they are coming to the shopping mall for their job and not coming with children.

B. Checklist for Selected Attributes

A checklist of selected attributes of Emerald Mall was developed through two major approaches of data collection, i.e., secondary data and primary data after the survey, as shown in Table II.

Table II: Checklist for Selected Attributes

Attributes	Sub Attributes	References from Literature Review; Standards & Scholars	Observations
Recreational Facilities	Food Court	[26], [31], [32], [33], [34], [35], [48], [49] and [51].	Food Court was under renovation while research was conducted during the period from February 2019 to September 2019 during multiple visits to the mall.

			It was observed that the food court was congested and small in size.
	Play Area	[26], [33], [34] and [35].	It was observed that there was insufficient space and no informal seating in the play area at Emerald Mall. The play area is near the food court, which is comfortable.
	Fitness Club	[26].	The fitness club was on the fourth floor; hence, many respondents didn't know about the existence of the fitness club. Shopkeepers use the facility occasionally, but not very often.
	Baby Chair	[26] and [27].	It was observed that baby chairs were missing in the mall.
	Atrium/ Exhibition Hall	[28], [31], [32], [33], [34], [35], [48], [50], [51] and [52].	The same is the case with the atrium/exhibition space in the central area of a mall, which was also not there.
	Free Wi-Fi	[29].	In addition to this, free Wi-Fi was also not present.
	Cinema Hall	[30], [31], [33], [34], [35] and [51].	The Cinema hall was not there. It was observed that at first there was a Jest five-dimensional (5D) movie theatre, whereas now it is not available.

C. Findings/Results: Effective Impacts of Specific Attributes on User Comfort

The findings of the research are summarized below, according to the recreational facilities of the shopping mall discussed:

The overview of the chosen facility is given below:

- Chairs with armrests and baby chairs were missing from the food court of Emerald Mall.
- The food court contained enough seating space in a congested and small area for the customers, and was easily accessible and located on the correct floor.
- The renovation was in progress in the food court of Emerald Mall.
- It was observed that there was insufficient space and no informal seating in the play area at Emerald Mall. The play area is near the food court, which is comfortable.
- The fitness club was not situated in a suitable place; it was on the fourth floor, so many respondents didn't know about its existence.
- At first, there was a Jest five-dimensional (5D) movie theatre, but now it is not available.
- However, it was observed that baby chairs, an atrium, an exhibition hall, an open space in the central area of a mall, Wi-Fi, and a cinema hall were not there.

Emerald Mall lacked the necessary facilities, which are highly recommended to be provided. It did not greatly offer these selected attributes in terms of user facilitation, and it seemed to focus much more on retail services. These

attributes are largely recreational facilities, and they certainly invite multiple customers to shopping malls.

D. Discussion

It can be said that, according to the observations carried out on the Emerald Mall, its status comprises of these attributes that are under study, namely, recreational facilities. There were a few activities set out as recreational facilities; the food court is one of them. The children liked the visits to the mall primarily because of the prospect of food and a snack. The food court that comes to the forefront greatly assists the consumer masses in staying for a longer time and at ease within the shopping malls. This is one of the reasons for increasing the number of users in the mall, as it is comfortable for many users to have a nice meal break while shopping or a good snack otherwise if they are in the mall for a hangout with family and friends. It was observed that the food court area was small. The food court does not have chairs with armrests and baby chairs. The children's play area, which is for the purpose of children's entertainment, was on the third floor of Emerald Mall. A family play area is offered to make a family visit enjoyable for all. In the play area, electronic games, physical games, and board games were mostly used. The provision of a play area has also enhanced the user comfort level as it provides a good opportunity for the mothers to complete their shopping or any other relevant work with peace of mind and safety. The play area was small in size and had no informal seating. The design of the play area was good and accessible to all, and its door was wide enough. The play area was near the food court, which was convenient. A fitness club (gym) is a place that houses exercise equipment for the purpose of physical exercise. It was on the fourth floor; hence many respondents didn't know about the existence of the fitness club. Shopkeepers use the facility occasionally, but not very often. This facility has addressed some of the particular types of users for their comfort who are in the mall only for the use of the fitness club. The Baby Chair supports the baby's mental development. Many children's chairs are designed with soft padded seats and different adjustable positions to provide extreme comfort for the baby. Children who cannot sit straight may sit straight and have a pleasant meal time in reclining positions. The baby chair was not in the Emerald Mall. The unavailability of this facility, particularly for the restaurants and other eating areas in the food court, causes problems for some of the customers. It would have added to the user's comfort if the baby chair had been provided. The atrium/exhibition hall/open space in the mall's central area was missing. It is the area between the long rows of stores. Public events such as holiday celebrations and exhibitions can go on. The exhibition hall is a much-specified space, and the comfort of the users is also relevant only to the particular users of the space. Therefore, the user's comfort in this regard is restricted because this user facility is unavailable. Wi-Fi has the advantage of allowing you to connect several devices to a single network. It prevents you from using data on your phone. You may connect from a considerable distance away from your modem without using a long connection, and there's a lot more. Wi-Fi was not open to all. This is an extended kind of facility, so the user's comfort in this

regard is restricted only to the shopkeepers. In this mall, there was a Jest Five-Dimensional (5D) movie theatre, which people visited this mall primarily to go to the movies. The research was conducted during the period from February 2019 to September 2019 during multiple visits to the mall. The movie theatre was provided some years back and is now no longer available. This service is no longer available, so it does not contribute to the user's comfort and leisure in this regard. Shopping malls deliver the entertainment needs of modern urban people. These assembled enterprises have an integrated cinema hall that will ensure customers have a nice time. Visitors to shopping malls are encouraged to spend more time there because of these entertainment options.

In a summarized form, it was found that Emerald Mall did not offer many attributes and seemed to focus much more on retail services. These attributes, mainly recreational facilities, act positively in attracting many people to shopping malls.

VI. CONCLUSION

The Emerald Mall has some recreational facilities that were improper in many respects, while some of the necessary facilities were suggested to be provided. The non-vibrant character of the Emerald Mall was the reason that the number of customers in this mall was generally lower than in other malls. It was concluded that the food court was small in size. The majority of shopkeepers used food courts occasionally, while some shopkeepers used food courts every day. A self-service system was there. The food court was well considered in terms of its nearness to the play area. But during the case study, the food court was under renovation. This shopping mall's food court came to the forefront as sub-units. This assisted the consumer masses in staying for a longer time and at ease within the shopping malls. Likewise, on the top floor, a food court was located so that by the time the individual arrives, he or she feels hungry and can make the most of the available space. It was ensured that the play area was accessible to all, so everybody could share the experience. The play area's door was wide enough. There was insufficient space and no informal seating in the play area at Emerald Mall. The fitness club was situated in an unsuitable place; it was on the fourth floor, so many respondents didn't know about the existence of the fitness club. At first, there was a Jest Five-Dimensional (5D) movie theatre, but now it is not available. Moreover, it was concluded that some of the most important facilities among recreational facilities were missing: baby chairs, Atrium/Exhibition Hall/Open space in the central area of a mall, Wi-Fi, and cinema hall.

Emerald Mall was not appropriately offering these selected attributes in terms of user facilitation and seemed to focus much more on retail services. These features, which are mostly recreational facilities, play a significant role in attracting a large number of customers to shopping malls.

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS/ SUGGESTIONS

The research culminates in several different ways that suggest some of the key points regarding recreational facilities that need to be addressed in order to enhance the user facilities. It was recommended that the food court be

extended. The mall should have some chairs with armrests and some baby chairs. Similarly, there should be informal seating inside the play area. This will improve communication between parents/guardians and caregivers. The play area should be expanded to include wheelchairs and strollers also. A fitness club should be in a suitable place so everyone can reach it for whole-body wellness: increased energy levels, reduced body pain, improved balance and flexibility, stress relief, decreased anxiety, and better sleep. Furthermore, it was recommended that baby chairs, an atrium/exhibition hall/open space in the central area of a mall, Wi-Fi, and a cinema hall be in a mall because if these facilities are provided, the users will have comfort and leisure, and they would highly prefer coming to this mall keeping these facilities in mind and will recommend others to visit at least once. These facilities cater to parents who are on a visit to the mall.

It is recommended to focus on recreational facilities for user comfort. This proceeds categorically by inviting numerous customers to shopping malls. The shopping mall designers should consider the recommended attributes according to standards as these attributes play a vital role in attracting customers to preferably visit Emerald Mall.

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Authors Contributions

The contribution of the authors was as follows: Reena Majid Memon's contribution to this study was the concept, technical implementation, paper writing and correspondence. The methodology to conduct this research work was proposed by Bushra Danish Talpur. Data collection and supervision were performed by Yasira Naeem Pasha. Sohrab Ahmed Marri facilitated the data compilation and validation. Nazia Iftakhar's contribution was project administration, and paper writing.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest and confirm that this work is original and not plagiarized from any other source, i.e., electronic or print media. The information obtained from all of the sources is properly recognized and cited below.

Data Availability Statement

The testing data is available in this paper.

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